

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020 WITH THE EXISTING NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY OF 1986

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Abstract :

While education leads to economic and social advancement, a country's education strategy at the school and college levels must be well defined and futuristic. To make it efficient, many nations use distinct education systems that take into account tradition and culture and adopt different stages of their life cycle at the school and college education levels. The Government of India has launched a new education strategy based on suggestions from an expert group led by Dr. Kasturirangan. This article examines numerous initiatives stated in the higher education system and compares them to the system in place now. The advantages of various innovations and projected consequences of NEP 2020 on the Indian higher education system are explored. Finally, some recommendations are made.

Key words: *Creativity, intelligence, fluency, flexibility, originality, gender*

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Introduction :

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, mankind has experienced a near-total metamorphosis during the last 8–9 months. Life as we know it has changed in certain ways. We have already turned into a new planet, and we have become obsolete. order/system, a system ruled by Covid-19 and regulated by Covid-19 and governed by Covid-19 and governed by Covid-19 and governed by Covid-19 all of the challenges that are associated with it. “We cannot solve our problems with the same mentality we used to create them,” Albert Einstein famously said. As a result, the current problems, particularly those linked to education and the execution of policies related to it, cannot be handled using older/erroneous policies, as a consequence and by the same reasoning. With the changing India, or the developing “new” India, education policy has to be redesigned and remade. Life must continue. After experiencing all of the “lockdowns/ curfews” and other isolating occurrences, one realises that, despite all of the restrictions/limitations and taboos, life is a dynamic and continuously changing process in which only the fittest survive. The expression “survival of the fittest” was adopted by Charles Darwin from Herbert Spencer’s original text in his 1864 book “Principles of Biology.” The emphasis is on the phrase “fittest,” which is certainly accurate, whether emphasised by Darwin or not:

“It is not the strongest of the species that survives, nor the most clever that survives.” It’s the one that can adapt to change the most.”

Objectives of the Study :

1. To identify the innovations in the new national higher education policy 2020,
2. To highlight and summarise the policies of the newly accepted higher education system,
3. To compare National Education Policy 2020 with the currently adopted policy in India,
4. To forecast the effects of NEP 2020 on India’s higher education system.

Methodology :

The technique entails a conceptual examination of the core of the national educational policy framework, as well as emphasising major elements of the NEP 2020 programme and comparing it to existing education policy. Using the focus group discussion approach to identify the innovations developed. The policy’s ramifications are examined using the predictive analysis approach. Many suggestions are made based on the findings of the focus groups.

Comparison of New Nep 2020 with Existing Nep :

The 1986 National Education Policy emphasised the use of information technology to modernise the education system. Teacher education, early childhood care, women’s empowerment, and adult literacy all received more focus. It was also suggested that giving universities and colleges more autonomy would increase the quality of education services. However, the NEP 1986 failed to increase educational quality by producing graduates with employable skills and by producing research output in the form of patents and scholarly articles. To make up for earlier NEP failures, NEP 2020 proposes a liberal education to foster interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary education and research at the undergraduate and graduate levels.

Table 1

Comparison of National Education policy 1986 & National Education policy 2020

New Education Policy 2020	National Policy of Education 1986
1 Ministry of Education	Ministry of Human Resource Development
2 Gross Enrolment Ratio -50%(2035)	Gross Enrolment Ratio-26.3% (2018)
3 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 format	10 + 2 format
4 Break-up of age:3-8,8-4,11-14,14-18	Break-up of age: 6-16,16-18
5 Exam-class 3, 5, 8, 10, 12	Exam-Each year up to class12
6 Board exam-objective and description, Twice a year	Board exam-Descriptive,Once a year
7 No hard separation of Art, Commerce, Science.All will be mixed with curriculum	Hard separation-Art, Commerce, Science

8	Curriculum content will be reduced to its core essentials	No such policy
9	One vocational subject is must-class 6 to 8	Not mandatory in existing format
10	Bag-less days encouraged	No such policy
11	Health card and check-up will be done	Health card and supplements programs are already running
12	360 degrees holistic report card for student including skills	No such policy
13	Coding to be taught from class 6 onwards	Not mandatory in existing format
14	3 language-by state, region and choice of student	3 language-Hindi, English and the Regional
15	Indian Sign Language students with hearing impairment to be developed by NIOs	No such policy
16	Pre-school to be added in KVS	Starts from class 1
17	Preparatory class Balvatika for children below the age of 5-by ECCE qualified teacher	Not mandatory in existing format
18	Report card to have reviewed from teachers, peers and students as well	Report card to have reviewed from Teachers
19	NCC wings-secondary and higher	NCC wings-secondary and higher

Further Suggestions for Improvements :

1. For permanent teaching positions in colleges and universities, a Ph.D. should be a requirement.
2. Leaders in higher education should be role models in terms of research and innovation.
3. Publication/Patent Requirement During Post-Graduate Courses
4. Compulsory Employability & Entrepreneurship papers in each semester to develop students' Employability & Entrepreneurship abilities.
5. Strict evaluation of National Research Foundation-funded projects by establishing a Research Output Based Credit Bank for all NRF members
6. Promotion to Open Access Publications with Copyright Retention for Authors
7. Elimination of Obsolescence in Higher Education
8. Increasing the capacity of the Integrated National Digital Library

Conclusion :

NEP 2020's findings and proposals are progressive in character. It brings a new appearance to the educational system, which is designed to be flexible and high-quality, and capable of moulding India into a lively society that

reflects our rich cultural past. NEP 2020 intends to build human resources who will generate value propositions, as opposed to the NPE 1986, which built a pool of educational system and trained human resources who contributed to the value chain of development. The Indian education system is ready to grow closer to international standards with the introduction of the new NEP 2020. In an online poll of 1103 students in India, over 96.4 percent expressed optimism about the outcomes of the execution of the plan. The NEP, which is intended to relieve students of the load of classroom teaching and examinations, will play a critical role in shaping the country's future. Its success, on the other hand, is dependent on consistent and transparent execution at all levels, as well as a fair allocation of resources. This enormous effort can only be accomplished with complete cooperation and participation from all parties, underpinned by institutional procedures.

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